

How concurrent thermomagnetic transitions can affect magnetocaloric effect: the $\text{Ni}_{49+x}\text{Mn}_{36-x}\text{In}_{15}$ Heusler alloy case

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Abstract:

It is usually claimed that structural and magnetic transitions should coincide to improve the total entropy change. Here we show that overlapping structural and magnetic transitions can compete with each other, which gives rise to some signature of the competition misinterpreted as an experimental artifact of the measurements as observed in $\text{Ni}_{49+x}\text{Mn}_{36-x}\text{In}_{15}$ (nominally $x = 0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5$ and 2.0) investigated in this work. Their various magnetic phase transitions show a low temperature conventional magnetocaloric effect (MCE), an inverse MCE followed by another high temperature conventional MCE. For concurrent phase transitions with their respective transition temperatures close to one another, an observed spike embedded in the high temperature conventional MCE region is found arising from the martensitic transformation. We show that a crossover of the magnetic field dependence of the transition temperatures is obtained for concurrent phase transitions occurring in a narrow temperature range. As an evidence of the complexity of overlapping phase transitions, a recently proposed quantitative method for determining the order of phase transition is applied to this compositional series, showing its applicability even to cases when first- and second-order phase transitions occur in a narrow temperature range.

Keywords: Magnetocaloric effect; phase transitions; Heusler alloys.

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Introduction

The current search for potential magnetocaloric materials for their applications and commercialization, is mainly centered on first-order thermomagnetic systems due to their accompanying large magnetocaloric effect (MCE) [1]. The discontinuous change in the entropy at transition temperatures in these systems give rise to large isothermal entropy change values, which are usually larger than that of the benchmark magnetocaloric material, Gd (which exhibits a second-order magnetic phase transition). In addition, some of them can also exhibit magnetostructural transitions to further contribute to the magnetocaloric response, which can be found for strong spin-lattice coupling alloy systems. As one of the representative examples of these systems, metamagnetic NiMn-based Heusler alloys are highly considered promising candidates for magnetic refrigeration due to their rare-earth-free compositions as well as large MCE, which is tunable to room temperature[1-6]. For $\text{Ni}_{0.50}\text{Mn}_{0.5-x}\text{In}_x$, ferromagnetic coupling was reported for both their austenitic and martensitic states for $0.15 \leq x \leq 0.16$ [7]. For $x \leq 0.16$, $\text{Ni}_{0.50}\text{Mn}_{0.34}\text{In}_{0.16}$ displayed an inverse MCE of $\sim 12 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ at 190 K ($\mu_0 \Delta H = 4 \text{ T}$) [8], which is far away from room temperature. However, the martensitic transformation could be tuned to 285 K [9], which is nearer to room temperature by varying the Ni/Mn ratio in $\text{Ni}_{0.50-y}\text{Mn}_{0.5+y}\text{In}_{0.15}$. Therefore, the magnetocaloric performance optimization of these alloys are mainly attained via compositional studies, especially so since their transition temperatures are highly compositional dependent. For example, the martensitic transition of Ni-Mn-X (X = Ga, Sn and In) increases with increasing electron per atom concentration (e/a) but the e/a ratio for these substituents affects the transition temperature of each series with a different slope[10]. Moreover, these alloys exhibit several magnetic phase transitions (martensitic transition, Curie transitions etc.) but their published magnetocaloric studies are mostly dedicated to their inverse MCE due to its giant magnitude for practical applications.

It is important to consider that, in a low symmetry single component magnetic material, both the Curie temperature and the breadth of the magnetic transition differ in single crystals with the field oriented along the easy and hard magnetization directions. As an example, a discussion on Gd single crystals can be found in Ref. [11]. Specifically in Heusler alloys, the cubic to tetragonal martensitic phase transformations requires three twin variants and for a single crystal, all will be present but their relative fractions can be varied by stress or field application [12,13]. For a single crystal after the martensitic transformation, the magnetic transition will necessarily involve averaging over configurations, considering the field orientation with respect to each of the twin variants. In a

polycrystalline sample, it will be more complicated due to the crystal orientations but still may be treated by averaging over configurations.

Furthermore, it has been considered that for Ni-Mn-X based alloy systems, their magnetic and lattice contributions to the total entropy change compete between each other [14], indicating that transition entropy change is optimal when the magnetic and martensitic phase transitions simultaneously occur though the associated adiabatic temperature change and refrigerant capacity do not follow this correlation [15]. From the magnetocaloric point of view, MCE will only be maximized if the different magnetic transitions are compatible, i.e. they both contribute to the magnetocaloric response as an additive manner. When the various transitions compete with one another, it results in a situation of overlapping phase transitions, which would no longer optimize the MCE. As previously mentioned, Heusler alloys exhibit several magnetic phase transitions, thus qualify for investigating the influence of overlapping phase transitions on MCE (MCE peaks at the maximum change of magnetization versus temperature, which is significantly affected by the nature of the overlapping transitions).

In this work, we study the MCE and thermomagnetic behavior of $\text{Ni}_{49+x}\text{Mn}_{36-x}\text{In}_{15}$ alloys (with nominal $x = 0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5$ and 2.0). They exhibit various MCE at different temperatures arising from their various magnetic phase transitions: a low temperature conventional MCE, an inverse MCE followed by another high temperature conventional MCE. Their concurrent phase transitions with close respective transition temperatures contribute to an observed spike embedded in the high temperature conventional MCE. Close examination of this feature reveals that it corresponds to its inverse MCE for magnetic fields of 0.9 T and above (not visible at low fields, except as a spike for $\sim 0.20 \leq \mu_0 H \leq 0.88$ T). These features could be misinterpreted as artifacts in the measurements. The tight phase overlap compensates the interpretations of the MCE peaks as well as the characteristic features in field dependence exponent (n) for such materials. The critical field to distinguish the respective transition temperatures of the concurrent phase transitions has been found as 0.2 T, whereby the austenitic phase formation starts to appear for magnetic fields larger than this value. The order of these transitions is analyzed using a recently proposed method [16] for the quantitative determination of the order of the phase transition.

Experimental

Polycrystalline $\text{Ni}_{49+x}\text{Mn}_{36-x}\text{In}_{15}$ alloys (with nominal $x = 0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5$ and 2) were arc melted in an argon-controlled atmosphere prior to a homogenization treatment under vacuum at 1123 K for 72 h . Their measured compositions, quantified using X-ray energy dispersive spectroscopy (XEDS) equipped on the field emission scanning electron microscope (Zeiss Ultra 55 FE-SEM), are tabulated in **Table 1**. The sample designation used in this work is according to their e/a ratio as tabulated in **Table 1**. Except for e/a 7.826 and 7.839 samples, all others show XRD (X-ray diffraction) results of monoclinic 7M modulated martensite at room temperature. The e/a 7.826 sample was found to exhibit a L2_1 austenitic structure from its XRD results at room temperature while e/a 7.839 sample displayed a combination of austenite and martensite. Further structural information can be found in ref.[17].

Table 1. Composition of $\text{Ni}_{49+x}\text{Mn}_{36-x}\text{In}_{15}$ alloys from XEDS characterization, their corresponding e/a ratios and sample designation used.

Nominal composition	Measured composition	e/a ratio
$\text{Ni}_{49}\text{Mn}_{36}\text{In}_{15}$	$\text{Ni}_{48.1}\text{Mn}_{36.5}\text{In}_{15.4}$	7.826
$\text{Ni}_{49.5}\text{Mn}_{35.5}\text{In}_{15}$	$\text{Ni}_{48.6}\text{Mn}_{35.9}\text{In}_{15.5}$	7.839
$\text{Ni}_{50}\text{Mn}_{35}\text{In}_{15}$	$\text{Ni}_{49.5}\text{Mn}_{35}\text{In}_{15.5}$	7.865
$\text{Ni}_{50.5}\text{Mn}_{34.5}\text{In}_{15}$	$\text{Ni}_{50.4}\text{Mn}_{34.4}\text{In}_{15.2}$	7.902
$\text{Ni}_{51}\text{Mn}_{34}\text{In}_{15}$	$\text{Ni}_{49.8}\text{Mn}_{34.8}\text{In}_{15.5}$	7.874

The magnetic behavior of the samples was characterized using a vibrating sample magnetometer. The isothermal magnetization vs magnetic field curves, $M(H)$, were performed using a discontinuous protocol[18]: (a) the sample was pre-cooled in zero field to a temperature value below its transition temperature; (b) then heated in zero field to the desired temperature (T) for measurement, (c) followed by measuring in increasing fields. The isothermal entropy change, ΔS_{iso} , was then indirectly determined from these magnetization measurements using Maxwell relation (where the initial magnetic field is zero):

$$\Delta S_{iso} = \mu_0 \int_0^H \frac{\partial M}{\partial T} dH \quad (1)$$

The calculation of ΔS_{iso} curves using this discontinuous characterization protocol will not lead to spurious results regardless of the order of the phase transition[18, 19].

The magnetic field dependence of ΔS_{iso} is described as a power law expression:

$$\Delta S_{iso} \propto H^n, \quad (2)$$

wherein the exponent n , which is field- and temperature-dependent[20], can be locally determined as:

$$n = \frac{d \ln |\Delta S_{iso}|}{d \ln H}. \quad (3)$$

Results and discussion

Coexistence of concurrent thermomagnetic phase transitions

Fig. 1 shows the $M(T)$ curves of the studied alloys measured at sweep rate of 0.005 Ks^{-1} at a field of 1.5 T , wherein the various magnetic phase transitions are observed to intersect one another before the completion of the previous one. At low temperatures, the e/a 7.826 sample shows a gradual decrease of its magnetization with temperature, which corresponds to the phase transition of its low temperature martensitic phase. At intermediate temperature of $\sim 240 - 260 \text{ K}$, its magnetization increases due to its martensitic transformation to austenite while the subsequent decreasing trend corresponds to the Curie transition of austenitic phase. The incompleteness of the magnetic phase transition of martensitic phase is also observed at 0.05 T (not shown). These are also observed for the other compositions studied in this work. Furthermore, the martensitic transition temperatures are observed to increase with e/a ratio.

Fig 1. $M(T)$ curves of the studied alloys measured at sweep rate of 0.005 Ks^{-1} for 1.5 T .

Fig. 2 shows the temperature dependence of ΔS_{iso} of the studied alloys for a maximum applied field of 1.5 T. The various MCE are presented as: bluish regions for inverse MCE and orangish for conventional MCE, whereby both are separated by the green dashed zero ΔS_{iso} line. Starting with the lowest e/a ratio, e/a 7.826 sample displays a conventional MCE at low temperatures (150-200 K), followed by an inverse MCE (225-250 K) then accompanied by another conventional MCE at higher temperatures (250-320 K). These various MCE peaks arise from (i) intermartensitic transitions around 150-200 K, whereby the Curie transition of the martensitic phase occurs at a Curie temperature (T_C^M) larger than that of the beginning of the martensitic transformation, then (ii) the martensitic transformation (martensitic temperature: T_M) followed by (iii) the Curie transition of austenite (Curie temperature of austenite: T_C^A) at higher temperatures. This is in agreement to its austenitic phase detected from its XRD results (performed at room temperature)[17]. In addition, it is worth noting that this sample shows the largest isothermal entropy change value in this work ($\Delta S_{iso}^{pk} = 12.28 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and an adiabatic temperature change of $\Delta T_{ad} = -4.15 \text{ K}$ for 1.8 T), which is also comparable to literature[3, 21]. However, increasing the e/a ratio severely affects the MCE value. The complexity of the different phase transitions can be easily observed from the different ΔS_{iso}^{pk} . Increasing the e/a ratio, the peak associated to the martensitic transition ($T_{pk(inverse \text{ MCE})}$) shifts to higher temperatures. However, the shape of the curve becomes anomalous for e/a 7.865 and 7.874 samples, for which a spike seems to be embedded into the high temperature conventional MCE, resembling a feature that could be associated to a measurement artifact (it is observed to be located in the region of inverse MCE around 323 K for e/a 7.874 sample). The physical relevance of this spike was also checked by repeating the measurements and combined with the discontinuous measurement protocol.

Fig 2. Isothermal entropy change as a function of temperature for $\text{Ni}_{49+x}\text{Mn}_{36-x}\text{In}_{15}$ alloys. For guide to the eye, the inverse and conventional MCE are projected as blue and orange regions, respectively. The green line corresponds to zero isothermal entropy change. For e/a 7.826 and 7.839 samples, their low temperature conventional MCE are further magnified in the insets of their plots.

The narrow distance of peaks between the inverse and high temperature conventional MCE also affected the visibility of their peak ΔS_{iso} values (i.e. $|\Delta S_{iso}^{pk}|$), which remain rather small for these two samples. As we will show later, magnetic field will act as a control parameter necessary for the separation of concurrent phase transitions.

To unequivocally ascertain that those spikes were not experimental artifacts, the $T_{pk(inverse\ MCE)}$ (for 1.5 T) are compared to the onset temperatures of austenite formation from DSC data (**Fig. 3**). There is an outstanding agreement between the T_M data obtained from DSC and magnetic measurements, indicating that the previously mentioned spikes embedded at the conventional MCE at higher temperatures correspond to the T_M , despite e/a 7.865 sample did not show an inverse MCE. Furthermore, the e/a ratio dependence of T_M in **Fig 3** also shows that T_M increases with e/a ratio, in agreement with literature [10].

Fig 3. e/a ratio dependence of the martensitic transition temperatures obtained from calorimetric and magnetic measurements (latter data were obtained at the temperatures corresponding to the peak values of inverse MCE for an applied field of 1.5 T).

In addition, these results also agree with the XRD data: e/a 7.826 sample shows a $L2_1$ austenitic phase at room temperature while those of e/a 7.865, 7.874 and 7.902 samples show 7M modulated martensite [17]. For e/a 7.839 sample, its XRD profile displays austenite and martensite at room temperature, in agreement to its DSC and magnetic observations.

Magnetic field dependence of the concurrent phase transitions

In order to ascertain the possibility of using the magnetic field as a control parameter to alter the overlapping of the phase transitions, the magnetic field dependence of e/a 7.874 sample was further studied. As the e/a 7.826 sample exhibits the most separated phase transitions among the series, it has been used as a reference for this work. The temperature dependence (upon heating) of the AC susceptibility (real χ' and imaginary χ'' parts) for an AC excitation field of 5 Oe at a frequency of 10 kHz at selected bias fields for both samples are shown in **Fig. 4**. For e/a 7.826 sample, there is a sharp increase in χ' at ~ 260 K and abrupt decrease at ~ 318 K for zero field (**Fig. 4(a)**), wherein the former corresponds to the appearance of the austenitic phase and the latter indicates the ferromagnetic-

paramagnetic transition (FM-PM) of the austenite (as indicated before, the peak occurring at ~200 K should correspond to inter-martensitic transitions, which is not relevant for the scope of this paper). For the imaginary part χ'' (**Fig. 4(b)**), the first sharp increase is followed by a gradual decrease of χ'' , subsequently followed by a narrow peak at the Curie transition. For higher bias magnetic fields, the shapes of the curves are modified with two distinct features: a relatively abrupt change of susceptibility at the martensitic transition and a peak related to the Curie transition. It is evident that both features get more separated with applied field: the T_M shifts to lower temperatures (more visible in the imaginary part of the susceptibility) while there is a shift to higher temperatures of the feature corresponding to the Curie transition (susceptibility peak for both components). For e/a 7.874 sample at zero bias field, one single feature is observed (at ~318 K) for both χ' and χ'' (**Figs. 4 (c) and (d)**), suggesting the overlapping of the transitions. In addition, a linear fit to the zero-field inverse susceptibility vs. temperature at higher temperatures (not shown) enabled the determination of the paramagnetic T_C (found to be at ~313 K, which agrees with that obtained by the steepest slope of χ'). For 1 T, T_M is observed at ~320 K (from the steepest slope of χ'') while T_C is observed at higher temperatures as determined from the peak of susceptibility. For a bias field of 5 T, the separation of these two transitions further increases. It has to be noted that T_C is not the Curie temperature of the austenite as, by definition, T_C^A should be field independent. However, magnetic field promotes the magnetic moment of the phase above its Curie temperature, making it more detectable in any magnetic measurement (like susceptibility or isothermal entropy change).

Fig 4. AC Susceptibility data at selected magnetic fields: (a) real χ' and (b) imaginary χ'' parts for e/a 7.826 sample; (c) χ' and (d) χ'' for e/a 7.874 sample.

The field dependence of transition temperatures ($T_{transition}$) and ΔS_{iso} of e/a 7.874 sample are presented in **Figs. 5 (a)** and **(b)** respectively. The $T_{transition}$ were obtained from the temperature of the maximum inverse MCE ($T_{pk(inverse\ MCE)}$) and high temperature conventional MCE except for T_M at zero field, which was not detectable from ΔS_{iso} , so it was determined from DSC data. With increasing magnetic fields, it is observed that $T_{pk(inverse\ MCE)}$ decreases (in agreement to literature wherein T_M decreases with magnetic fields [22-24]) while T_C increases instead. In addition, these give rise to a crossover occurring at ~ 0.2 T: for larger fields, T_M and T_C^A can be distinguished while T_M is not detectable by magnetic methods below this field. This is further evidenced in **Fig. 5 (b)**, where an additional magnetic phase transition is observed at 0.2 T and above. At low fields (i.e. < 0.2 T), the MCE of e/a 7.874 sample shows that it undergoes a single thermomagnetic phase transition (see the curve for 0.1 T in **Fig. 5 (b)**). However, with increasing fields, the presence of an additional phase transition is visible: a shoulder can be observed at 320 – 324 K for 0.2 T. At higher fields of 0.3 T and above, a second ΔS_{iso} peak can be observed, which laterally increases with fields. For 0.9 T (inset), the point at 322 K shifts to positive ΔS_{iso} , developing into an artifact-like feature embedded in the conventional MCE. It has to be noted that the temperature resolution for the MCE experiments of e/a 7.874 sample is 1 K.

Moreover, the lowest magnetic field that enabled the visibility of additional phase transition occurring in this sample agrees with that at the crossover observed in **Fig. 5 (a)**. These highlight that magnetic field acts as the control parameter of the concurrent phase transitions with $T_{transition}$ close to one another for such samples.

Fig 5. Magnetic field dependence of (a) $T_{pk(inverse\ MCE)}$ and T_C (obtained from magnetic data except $T_{pk(inverse\ MCE)}$ at zero field, which was obtained from DSC) and (b) $\Delta S_{iso}(T)$ for e/a 7.874 sample. At the crossover of ~ 0.2 T and fields above it, the various $T_{transition}$ can be distinguished while the visibility of the MCE peak arising from T_M only crosses to positive ΔS_{iso} at 0.9 T (inset) and above.

Order of the thermomagnetic phase transitions

Magnetocaloric materials are mainly classified into their order of thermomagnetic phase transitions: first-order (FOPT) or second-order phase transitions (SOPT). The former usually exhibits a more abrupt MCE than the latter but traded off by a narrow temperature span and hysteresis. Hence, the ideal magnetocaloric material with a large MCE without hysteresis would be in-between the two categories, laying in the region termed as the critical point of SOPT. For that, distinguishing of the order of phase transitions is an important evaluation of magnetocaloric materials. The methods for the identification of the order of phase transitions are typically dependent on a clear separation between different phase transitions or they require deconvolution of the different features. These deconvolution procedures typically require extensive calculations and are therefore prone to misinterpretations. Recently, a new quantitative criterion based on the MCE has been proposed and applied to numerical models as well as different alloys and compounds[16]. In addition, the use of this new criterion further discloses a drastic alteration of the order of thermomagnetic phase transitions by very minor compositional changes despite retaining the same crystal space group[25]. This technique could surpass the accuracy of the typical methods used for identification of the order of magnetic phase transitions, in particular to those based on qualitative features observed in the data as well as for compositions very near to the critical point of SOPT[26]. However, up to now, with the cases where phase transitions overlapped with other type of phase transitions have not been studied. Due to the intricate character of the series of transitions observed in this work they constitute a good testing ground to evaluate the applicability of this new criterion in $\text{Ni}_{49+x}\text{Mn}_{36-x}\text{In}_{15}$. **Fig. 6** shows the temperature dependence of exponent n and ΔS_{iso} for $\text{Ni}_{49+x}\text{Mn}_{36-x}\text{In}_{15}$ compounds for 1.5 T. The magenta dotted line corresponds to $n = 2$ while the green dash line to $\Delta S_{iso} = 0$. For this figure, the inverse MCE is shaded teal in color. For e/a 7.826 sample, its exponent n lies around 1 at low temperatures then abruptly changes at the range of $213 < T < 218$ K, whereas ΔS_{iso} switches from negative to positive as highlighted in the light blue region (i.e. conventional to inverse MCE). This characteristic feature agrees with the $n(T)$ behavior of a Heusler alloy reported in ref.[16].

Next, an overshoot of $n > 2$ (highlighted by the cyan shade) is observed for ~ 235 to ~ 243 K (near $T_{pk(\text{inverse MCE})}$), which indicates the FOPT nature of its inverse MCE. Subsequently, n decreases to the characteristic spikes arising from the alteration of ΔS_{iso} signs near 247 – 258 K (light blue region), analogous with literature[16]. At

higher temperatures (not shown in the figure), typical n behavior for a SOPT is observed: a minimum at T_C^A and n increasing towards the value of 2 at higher temperatures (paramagnetic region). A similar $n(T)$ trend for the regions of the low temperature conventional MCE and inverse MCE are also observed for e/a 7.839 sample, where there is a closer overlapping of the transitions: at low temperatures, a minimum n is observed at ~ 185 K, which corresponds to the T_C of the low temperature conventional MCE, then gradually increases to larger values till ~ 248 K. This observation suggests that the T_C of the low temperature martensite overlaps with T_M , whereby the austenite phase starts to form before the T_C of martensitic phase (so n could not approach towards the value of 2). The characteristic spikes from switching the ΔS_{iso} signs are observed at $283 < T < 288$ K (light blue region) then followed by an overshoot of $n > 2$ (cyan) near the $T_{pk(inverse\ MCE)}$, indicating a FOPT for the inverse MCE. As the inverse MCE is closely accompanied by the high temperature conventional MCE, the resulted characteristic spikes are observed to be compensated by the mixture of competing phases (they are less separated from each other compared to those in e/a 7.826 sample). At higher temperatures, a minimum is observed at the T_{pk} of the high temperature conventional MCE (also the T_C^A). As for e/a 7.874 sample, it shows a pronounced influence of concurrent phase transitions near the inverse MCE within 318 – 324 K unlike the former two samples (of lower e/a ratio). The phase overlaps are observed from the overshoot of $n > 2$, highlighted as cyan shaded region (at the $T_{pk(inverse\ MCE)}$), closely surrounded by the characteristic spikes of switching the ΔS_{iso} signs (light blue regions): first at the range of 318 – 321 K and closely accompanied within 322 – 324 K. At higher temperatures, n tends towards a maximum value of 2, which corresponds to the paramagnetic region and agrees with the approach of the conventional MCE towards zero ΔS_{iso} . The inverse MCE for e/a 7.874 sample occurs in the midst of the high temperature conventional MCE, indicating a strong competition in the phase transitions occurring within this temperature range ($318 < T < 324$ K), in agreement with previously discussed results. Hence, this could attribute to the unseen characteristic features arising from ΔS_{iso} signs switching as compared to those observed for e/a 7.826 and 7.839 samples (the tighter gap between the light blue regions for e/a 7.874 can also illustrate its competitive phase overlap).

Fig 6. Temperature dependence of exponent n (solid symbols) and ΔS_{iso} (open symbols) for $\text{Ni}_{49+x}\text{Mn}_{36-x}\text{In}_{15}$ alloys for 1.5 T. The magenta dotted line corresponds to $n = 2$ while the green dash line to $\Delta S_{iso} = 0$.

As magnetic field previously acts as the control parameter for the concurrent phase transitions occurring in e/a 7.874 sample, the magnetocaloric behavior at higher fields are further analyzed and presented in **Fig. 7**. A clear abrupt inverse MCE ($\Delta S_{iso} = 9.53 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ at 317.5 K) is observed between the conventional MCE for 9 T without any ambiguity of the previously perceived artifact-looking spike embedded in the high temperature conventional MCE. Hence, the overshoot of $n > 2$ (cyan) for 9 T is now clearly observed near the $T_{pk(\text{inverse MCE})}$ while the characteristic spikes of switching from inverse to the high temperature conventional MCE are observed at higher temperature tail region.

Fig 7. (a) $\Delta S_{iso}(T)$ for 9T and (b) $n(T)$ at 9 T for e/a 7.874 sample. The shaded teal region in (a) represents the inverse MCE while the cyan in (b) indicates the overshoot of $n > 2$.

Conclusions

$\text{Ni}_{49+x}\text{Mn}_{36-x}\text{In}_{15}$ Heusler alloys belong to a class of promising materials for various applications arising from their peculiar magnetostructural properties. For that, they exhibit various thermomagnetic phase transitions, arising from the low temperature martensite, martensitic transformation and high temperature austenite (both are magnetic phases). In this paper, we had shown that these various phase transitions of $\text{Ni}_{49+x}\text{Mn}_{36-x}\text{In}_{15}$ can affect their performance analysis when encountering concurrent phase transitions of respective transition temperatures close to each other. Overall, these samples exhibit various MCE at different temperatures: low temperature conventional MCE, inverse MCE followed by another high temperature conventional MCE. Unlike other results presented in literature, we observe that the competition of the different phase transitions does not necessarily improve the magnetocaloric response, detecting the largest ΔS_{iso} values when the martensitic and Curie transitions are most separated. For samples with e/a ratios of 7.865 and 7.874, a spike embedded in the high temperature conventional MCE is observed. This feature corresponds to the inverse MCE as its corresponding temperature agrees with the starting temperature of austenitic phase formation detected from calorimetric. The first-order nature of the martensitic transition had been identified by the overshoot of field exponent larger than 2 based on the recently proposed quantitative criterion using MCE. Due to the contributions of the tight phase overlap, compensated visibility of the characteristic features in their field dependence exponent are observed, in agreement to their MCE behavior. Furthermore, when using magnetic field dependence studies, we show that a critical field value of ~ 0.2 T could act as the control parameter to distinguish the overlapping magnetic phase transitions and identify the martensitic transformation. The zero field susceptibility data of the sample with e/a ratio of 7.874 show a single magnetic phase transition. However, with magnetic fields larger than the critical value, it shows that its martensitic transformation occurs prior to the completion of the Curie transition of its low temperature martensite then closely accompanied by the Curie transition of the high temperature austenitic phase, all in all, in agreement to the other discussed experimental results. Therefore, the critical magnetic field to distinguish the visibility of the concurrent phase transitions, especially with respective transition temperatures very close to each other, as well as the recently proposed quantitative criterion are useful to study the phase complexity of such magnetic materials. In addition, this quantitative method to identify the order of phase transitions is successfully extended in this paper to materials with overlapping transitions.

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